

THE MODEL FOR DEVELOPING CREATIVE AND CRITICAL THINKING IN FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS.

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kreativ va tanqidiy fikrlashini rivojlantirish uchun tavsiya etilgan model taqdim etiladi. Modelning asosiy maqsadi o'qituvchilarda mustaqil fikrlash, innovatsion g'oyalarni yaratish va pedagogik vaziyatlarda tanqidiy yondoshuvlarni shakllantirishdir. Modellar pedagogik jarayonda o'qituvchilarga kreativ va tanqidiy fikrlashni birgalikda rivojlantirishga imkon beradigan metodlarni taqdim etadi. Kreativ va tanqidiy fikrlash o'qituvchilarning o'quvchilarga ta'lim berish usullarini takomillashtirishga yordam beradi. Model o'qituvchilarga ilg'or pedagogik metodlarni qo'llash imkoniyatini yaratadi.

Tayanch tushunchalar: Kreativ fikrlash, tanqidiy fikrlash, pedagogik model, innovatsion ta'lim, kasbiy malaka, o'qituvchilarning shaxsiy rivojlanishi, pedagogik metodlar.

Аннотация

В данной статье представлен модель развития креативного и критического мышления у будущих учителей начальных классов. Основная цель модели – развитие у учителей независимого мышления, создание инновационных идей и формирование критического подхода к педагогическим ситуациям. Модели предлагают методы, которые позволяют одновременно развивать креативное и критическое мышление в педагогическом процессе. Креативное и критическое мышление помогает учителям совершенствовать методы преподавания и повышать их эффективность. Модель создает условия для применения передовых педагогических методов в образовательной практике.

Ключевые понятия: Креативное мышление, критическое мышление, педагогическая модель, инновационное образование, профессиональная квалификация, личностное развитие учителей, педагогические методы.

Annotation

This article presents a model for developing creative and critical thinking in future primary school teachers. The main goal of the model is to foster independent thinking, generate innovative ideas, and develop critical

approaches to pedagogical situations. The model provides methods that allow for the simultaneous development of both creative and critical thinking in the educational process. Creative and critical thinking helps teachers improve their teaching methods and enhance their effectiveness. The model creates opportunities for applying advanced pedagogical methods in teaching.

Key words: Creative thinking, critical thinking, pedagogical model, innovative education, professional qualification, teachers' personal development, pedagogical methods.

Reforms in higher pedagogical education and its modernization require professors to demonstrate initiative, a creative approach, and the ability to foster independent thinking in future primary school teachers during the teaching process. In higher pedagogical education, the lesson is the primary field for pedagogical creativity. The teacher's main pedagogical need—teaching and delivering content—is carried out precisely in the lesson process. Therefore, the lesson demands an innovative approach and a new attitude towards organizing the higher pedagogical education process. In the process of standardized lessons, an important task for the teacher is to engage future primary school teachers in acquiring advanced modern knowledge and to move them forward towards innovative education.

This, in turn, involves engaging both the teacher and future primary school teachers in collaborative work. For this, it is necessary to avoid forcing future primary school teachers in the teaching process. One of the characteristics of pedagogical collaboration is to eliminate fear in the future primary school teacher during the lesson, ensuring their freer and more confident participation, convincing them of their own abilities, and viewing them as individuals capable of serious and creative work.

The breadth (wide and narrow) and depth of thinking are related to the continuity of theory and practice. Practice is the criterion for the correctness of judgment. Independence of thinking involves the ability to apply general experience, having personal opinions, and reflecting on experience.

Creative and critical thinking is based on the ability to express one's own thoughts on a given issue or problem, creatively and critically reinterpret the thoughts of others, and justify and maintain one's own point of view. To clarify this concept further, thinking is a process similar to reading, writing, speaking, and listening. It is an active, coordinating process that encompasses thoughts about some truth.

The importance of creative and critical thinking is as follows (Figure 1):

Figure 1. The Importance of Creative and Critical Thinking.

The foundation of creative and critical (analytical) thinking in the educational process:

1. It fosters mutual respect between the teacher (pedagogue) and the student, as well as between the student and the future primary school teacher.
2. The student-future primary school teacher's personal experience is utilized during the lesson process.
3. Specific educational content is used in accordance with and in a clear manner that aligns with the future primary school teacher's requirements.
4. Educational materials are used in solving problems.
5. Various ideas and perspectives are integrated.
6. Initial conditions are accepted and tested.
7. The education process is carried out through the relationships between the teacher (pedagogue) and the student-future primary school teachers, or between the student-future primary school teachers themselves.
8. Conditions are created for the independent learning of student-future primary school teachers, and methods are selected according to their level of preparedness.

In the dissertation, the model for developing the creative and critical thinking of future primary school teachers has been improved by ensuring the proportionality of the integration of frontal and individual tasks in professional activity to stable quality indicators.

This model for developing the creative and critical thinking of future primary school teachers has been improved by determining the proportional relationship between the dynamic quality indicators aimed at ensuring the stability of the integration of frontal and individual tasks in professional activity and adapting it to the possibilities of didactic influence.

Frontal (collective) task – the goal is set for all learners to perform the same task.

Individual task (solo) – the task is performed individually by each learner, allowing for the simultaneous assessment of each future primary school teacher's readiness to learn, and it is characterized by the individual performance of the task.

In the classroom, reinforcement of acquired knowledge, skills, and competencies, expanding and deepening the educational material developed in the classroom, forming skills for independent completion of exercises, developing independent thinking based on performing individual tasks within the scope of the program material, collecting and preparing educational resources such as individual observations, newspaper and journal clips, statistical data, etc., can be accomplished.

Ensuring the proportionality of the integration of frontal and individual pedagogical tasks to stable quality indicators (proportional – if one of the quantities increases or decreases, the other also changes accordingly; proportional, harmonious) should be noted that integration means combining the goals and factors of teaching into a cohesive whole. Integration — from the Latin "integer" — wholeness, "integerara" – to complete, create, restore wholeness. Ensuring the coherence of the content in education is also a field of focus for integration.

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